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INCREMENTAL REFACTORING TO REDUCE TECHNICAL DEBT: MIGRATING FROM AN MVC MONOLITH TO MICROSERVICE APIS

Annotation

We report an incremental migration from a .NET MVC monolith to microservices (Web API, .NET 8). The Strangler Fig pattern and small behavior-preserving refactorings were applied. Progress was tracked with four KPIs (endpoint coverage, refactoring ratio, DB/Cache, NoSQL adoption) and aggregated by a bounded IMPI index. In four months, stage goals were met: DB load decreased and responsiveness improved without halting releases.

Keywords

technical debt, incremental refactoring, microservices, Strangler Fig, Redis, quality metrics.

Introduction

Technical debt is the cumulative cost of expedient decisions; unmanaged, it accrues «interest» that slows product evolution. Contemporary surveys emphasize embedding technical-debt management into daily development, rather than episodic campaigns [3]. A safe path for legacy modernization is the Strangler Fig pattern, which gradually replaces legacy functionality with a new contour until the old system is decommissioned [6]. Methodologically, our work relies on incremental refactoring—a sequence of small, behavior-preserving changes that improve internal structure and architecture [5].

Objectives and Rationale

The migration was motivated by:

1. Excessive backend calls.
2. High dependence on the relational DB with blocking under load, and business logic embedded in SQL procedures.
3. Stage objectives were to decouple layers, introduce caching, and move auxiliary data (JSON logs) into a document-oriented store to offload SQL [7].

Method and Stages

Migration proceeded without release freezes. Existing MVC endpoints began proxying parts of logic to new Web APIs (.NET 8), enabling progressive decoupling.

We applied Strangler Fig: new capabilities moved to microservices while legacy controllers temporarily served as facades [6].

Technical decisions: aggressive caching (Redis), feature toggles, telemetry for DB/cache calls, and relocation of logs and semi-structured documents to MongoDB [7].

To aggregate heterogeneous improvements, we compare actual and target for each metric—making components dimensionless and comparable.

1. Endpoints in API (E_t): target coverage $\geq 30\%$.
2. Refactoring Ratio (R_t): target share $\geq 15\%$ of commits are refactorings.
3. DB/Cache Ratio (D_t): target is a $2\times$ reduction from baseline D_0 . Progress is the share of achieved reduction (formula (1) below).

4. NoSQL Adoption (N_t): target share of write operations in MongoDB $\geq 25\%$.

$$progress_D = \frac{D_0 - D_c}{D_0 - D_t} \quad (1)$$

where: D_0 —baseline DB/Cache ratio; D_c —current DB/Cache ratio; D_t —target DB/Cache ratio (here, two-fold reduction from baseline).

Integral Formula:

$$IMPI = \frac{\min\left(\frac{E_n}{E_t}, 1\right) + \min\left(\frac{R_r}{R_t}, 1\right) + \min\left(\frac{D_0 - D_c}{D_0 - D_t}, 1\right) + \min\left(\frac{N_s}{N_t}, 1\right)}{4} \quad (2)$$

where: E_n —current share of endpoints on the new API; E_t —target share of endpoints; R_r —actual Refactoring Ratio; R_t —target Refactoring Ratio; D_0 —baseline DB/Cache; D_c —current DB/Cache; D_t —target DB/Cache; N_s —current share of writes moved to MongoDB; N_t —target NoSQL share.

Results

To make the outcome actionable for practitioners, this section first reports the four-month actuals per KPI and their normalized contributions to the bounded IMPI, then presents the aggregate index.

Four-month actuals:

- Endpoints on API: 35%. $E_n/E_t = 0.35/0.30 = 1.17 \Rightarrow \min = 1.00$
- Refactoring Ratio: 17%. $R_r/R_t = 0.17/0.15 = 1.13 \Rightarrow \min = 1.00$
- DB/Cache: progress $D = (5.8-2.1) / (5.8-2.9) = 3.7/2.9=1.28 \Rightarrow \min = 1.00$
- NoSQL Adoption: 28%. $N_s/N_t = 0.28/0.25 = 1.12 \Rightarrow \min = 1.00$

Aggregate:

$$IMPI = \frac{1.00 + 1.00 + 1.00 + 1.00}{4} = 1.00 \quad (3)$$

Interpretation: all stage goals were met or exceeded while maintaining continuous delivery.

Discussion

Observed database offload and improved responsiveness align with existing evidence that technical debt management should be treated as a continuous engineering practice, with incremental refactoring serving as a fundamental technique to achieve it [2], [3], [5]. Our findings are also consistent with empirical research showing that improving package organization—by reducing inter-package coupling and eliminating cyclic dependencies—enhances maintainability and facilitates incremental refactoring in legacy systems [1]. At the architectural level, lowering the coupling within a system's core has been shown to reduce defect rates and overall maintenance overhead [4]. Furthermore, industry experience reports confirm the practicality of targeted refactorings and SOLID-oriented strategies for incrementally paying down architectural debt in mature systems [8].

Conclusion

The incremental migration from an MVC monolith to microservice APIs achieved, without release freezes: 35% endpoint coverage on the new contour, 17% refactoring ratio, DB/Cache reduced from 5.8 to 2.1, and 28% of writes moved to MongoDB. The bounded index $IMPI = 1.00$ indicates full attainment of stage goals. The methodology is transparent: metrics are normalized to targets; DB/Cache uses share-of-reduction from baseline.

References:

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